

What it is

Smart phone app that helps singing wannabes learn how to sing

How it works

- Learn by Exercise

How it works

- Learn by Songs

The image displays a digital music interface. It features a piano roll with a 5-line staff. The notes are represented by black rectangular markers with numbers 1 through 8. The lyrics 'ra', 'la', 'ta', and 'mat' are placed below the notes. A red vertical line indicates the current playback position. Below the staff are 'REC' and 'PLAY' buttons, and a 'Tempo' slider set to 'fast'.

For whom?

- Every singing enthusiast
- People who cannot afford singing coach
- Musical experience helps

What it is not

Ear training app

Karaoke app

What it is not

Ear training app

No fun!

Karaoke app

No learning!

Why use it?

- Discover what you like in music
- Prepare for karaoke the fun way

How to make money?

- Freemium model
 - Premium has more exercises
 - Song packs paid
- Advertisement
 - Web streaming platforms
 - Social networks